

Food Business and Recent Trends for Improving Implementation Strategies

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Introduction

Shiyo, A., & Keter, N. (2012) stated business is the exchange of goods for money. It entails the transfer of advantages for the mutual benefit of at least two parties. The objective is to provide benefit to both parties—profit for the seller and satisfaction for the customer's wants. But the hardest aspect of starting a business is coming up with a good business idea (Biz Foundry 2010). It could be a brand-new invention or a unique solution to a widespread problem. For a notion to be successful, it must be a viable business idea.

Businesses in the modern world are thought to be unable to prosper without planning. The business plan of a firm describes how the company will be managed and how it will operate. Westwood (2004) If organizations want to succeed in the current business environment, they must perform more extensive operational studies. According to the authors, detailed planning and the creation of a business plan can provide any company with a competitive edge.

Skrypnik, A. (2020) mentioned a business plan is a document that enables you to run a company. It should also be recognized as a powerful instrument for company management and may thus be viewed as an essential component of strategic planning and as a manual for execution and control.

A company strategy has five main functions in modern business practices:

- The first task involves the establishment of a business strategy and the probable use of a business plan. This position is crucial for both the phase of business development and for the creation of new directions.

- The second job function is planning. You can use it to evaluate the potential for managing internal processes and new product development.
- Without access to credit resources, it is currently difficult to operate any kind of business, so this function enables you to draw capital in the form of loans. However, because there are more instances of loan non-repayment, acquiring a loan can be difficult. The comprehensive business plan serves as the main criterion for approving or denying credit.
- To use equity or technologies, business owners might discover potential partners.
- Increased employee awareness of upcoming tasks, coordination of their efforts, task assignment, and desire to achieve goals.

Literature Review

Food Business

Skrypnik, A. (2020) said that the food sector is seen as a competitive field for investment. This fact is supported by the global trend for such institutions to grow by an average of 5% year. In contrast to other business sectors, restaurant services do not severely suffer from economic downturns. If a restaurant has a solid reputation, it will never lose customers.

The main objectives of food business are as follows:

- Analysis of the target market, considering the position of the customer in this market.
- Proposals to attract customers at certain stages of the business implementation.
- Focusing on profitable food organizations and biodegradable food package materials.
- Being up to date in the restaurant industry to attract the customers.

Only a project that considers production, financial considerations, and payback calculations can effectively deliver a concept. It is necessary to decide what actions must be made to achieve the

goal. It is challenging to find a pre-written business plan for a restaurant that includes calculations for any type of establishment. The owner can complete this task independently or with the aid of a professional who is acquainted with the issue (Boardman, 2017).

The restaurant business is a place where business owners engage in activities with the goal of making money and satisfying their customers. It is hard to be too specific in the restaurant industry because everything is crucial. The chef and the staff are interested in establishing unique circumstances to boost the location's appeal. They can raise the prices and sales if they succeed in doing that (Fields, 2014).

The first thing a restaurateur wants to know is how many potential customers there are. Every little expense made by the company could influence the result. It is uncommon for a restaurant to initially experience the number of customers anticipated; therefore, it is crucial to prepare for all eventualities. A restaurant's operation is a special system with many different parts, such as manufacturing, marketing, concentrating on specific consumer wants, conducting profit-based research and forecasts, and comprehending the organization's external and internal environments, among others.

Development of market behavior plans and techniques employing marketing programs is one of the most crucial tasks. To ensure pricing policy, demand formation, and simulation of sales, advertising, optimization of distribution channels, and sales organization, such programs are required to make specific measures for product quality improvement and expansion of the range of services, such as entertaining customers, competitors, and development of the competitive environment.

The restaurant industry is a complex system, and the level of success of this system depends on the actions and quality of interactions of all the structures within it at every level.

These interactions are assessed using a variety of criteria, including the appropriate location for the restaurant's premises, the complexity of potential conditions given the level of the restaurant, the appropriate restaurant concept, compliance with external and internal design, the caliber of the menu, and a variety of other factors.

The definition of the restaurant concept and its targeted audience, a marketing analysis that includes the strongest competitors, market capacity (the maximum number of customers you can expect), the availability of prerequisites in a city or region that could be suitable for your restaurant, and other factors make up the project implementation plan for the restaurant. putting together a thorough business plan for the restaurant that details the costs of starting up the business and running it, an analysis of monthly revenue, a forecast of when it will start to turn a profit, and an estimate of how long it would take the project to pay for itself.

Research question 1:

Do the consumers' demographic and psychographic traits and the restaurant chain they frequent differ noticeably from one another?

Research question 2:

What are the causing effects of food insecurity on people's health?

Method

Procedures

By using a correlative analysis method, survey sampling and measures were analyzed. Potential respondents were asked to take the survey using Qualtrics online. We used online social media like WhatsApp, GroupMe, Instagram to share our survey link to reach out to multiple people. We used Likert seven scale and created multiple-choice questions on demographics, food

brands and how they relate to consumer health and the standard of food produced in restaurants, sustainable food packaging systems in the food industry, strategies for preventing food insecurity, and demographic and psychographic influences on the food industry made up the survey. Additionally, participants' location included majority are from United States especially Oklahoma, Edmond cities and other states with 50.22% participants and 36.27% participants are from Indian states.

Sample

Of the sample of 93 participants, 32.97% were female and 67.032% were male. Participants age ranged from 0-66 or older. (Mean=4.49, Standard Deviation=0.95). In terms of race or ethnicity, 77.27% reported as Asians, 4.54% reported as American Indians, 6.8% reported as Hispanic or Latinos also African Americans and others include whites, and some preferred not to answer their race. When coming to the educational level of the survey participants, 42.86 % reported bachelor's degree, 40.04% reported master's degree, associate degree and higher education reported 3.64%, others reported to be 0.91, whereas rest of them did not prefer to answer.

Measures

Health vs preferred brand. Health preference was measured using the question. *Regardless of my health I would always go with my preferred brand.* Participants rated their maximum health preference by selecting the following scale of items: Of total 88 respondents, strongly agree = 6, agree = 23, somewhat agree = 14, neither agree nor disagree = 14, strongly disagree = 4, disagree = 23 and somewhat disagree = 5.

Researching restaurant vs advertising. The market of restaurants was measured using this question. *I will not prefer doing any research if the advertising of the restaurant is good.*

Participants rated their maximum health preference by selecting the following scale of items: Of total 90 respondents, strongly agree = 5, agree = 16, somewhat agree = 12, neither agree nor disagree = 8, strongly disagree = 7, disagree = 26 and somewhat disagree = 16.

Success level vs quality of interactions. Success level of restaurant was measured using this question. *The restaurant industry is a complex system, and the level of success of this system depends on the actions and quality of interactions of all the structures within it at every level.*

Participants rated their maximum health preference by selecting the following scale of items: Of total 88 respondents, strongly agree = 10, agree = 54, somewhat agree = 9, neither agree nor disagree = 8, strongly disagree = 1, disagree = 1 and somewhat disagree = 5.

Sustainable packaging. Sustainable packaging was measured using this question. *Switching to sustainable packaging is a preferable alteration in the food business.* Participants rated their maximum health preference by selecting the following scale of items: Of total 87 respondents, strongly agree = 17, agree = 37, somewhat agree = 14, neither agree nor disagree = 10, strongly disagree = 4, disagree = 5 and somewhat disagree = 0.

Food insecurity vs natural calamities. Prior planning was measured using this question. *Planning strategically would prevent food insecurity during natural calamities.* Participants rated their maximum health preference by selecting the following scale of items: Of total 87 respondents, strongly agree = 23, agree = 47, somewhat agree = 6, neither agree nor disagree = 8, strongly disagree = 0, disagree = 2 and somewhat disagree = 1.

Demographic and psychographic factors vs restaurant business. Influence of factors was measured using this question. *Do you think demographic and psychographic factors (like age, Income, education, employment, etc.) influence the restaurant business.* Participants rated their maximum health preference by selecting the following scale of items: Of total 87 respondents,

strongly agree = 11, agree = 32, somewhat agree = 16, neither agree nor disagree = 9, strongly disagree = 6, disagree = 11 and somewhat disagree = 2.

Results

Research Question 1: Do the consumers' demographic and psychographic traits and the restaurant chain they frequent differ noticeably from one another?

When asked about the demographic and psychographic traits that influence the restaurant business or not and health preferences, along with success of the restaurant. Then most of the people responses were:

Among the respondents 61 were between the age of 18 – 25 who mostly agreed (Strongly agree- 12.64%, Agree- 36.78%, Somewhat agree- 18.39%) with the point that they prefer a particular brand when preferring healthy food and this preference will associate with the restaurant business or chain. Whereas few people (35.23%) disagreed with the point and felt like there is no influence of any factors on restaurant business or chain. And the rest of the responses were the miscellaneous mostly of age groups from (26- 66 and above) where they neither agreed nor disagreed to the point.

On an average, most of the percentage who agreed to the discussion were male 67.03% whereas the rest 32.97% are female that agreed to the discussion.

Research question 2: What are the causing effects of food insecurity on people's health?

There are several reasons for food insecurity, like natural calamities and changes the packaging preferences to combat this kind of issue by planning ahead and choosing sustainable food packaging techniques. In this case the people responses were:

Most of the respondents 87.36% agreed (Strongly agree- 26.44%, Agree-54.02%, Somewhat agree- 6.90%) that planning helps to combat food insecurity. Whereas a few people (9.20%) neither agreed to the point nor disagreed and stayed neutral with the discussion. Remaining were miscellaneous percentages who disagreed with the point and stated planning ahead has no influence or impact on food insecurity.

Overall, most of the respondents who agreed with the discussion of planning ahead were Asians (77.27%) and the others were Hispanic and Black Americans, where few of them agreed to the discussion and few were neutral with their opinion.

Discussion

This study is to assess the people's opinion on restaurant business, success level, quality and health preference based on demographic, psychographic factors including Age, ethnicity, etc. using Likert scale. Also, studying modern techniques like sustainable food packaging. There were varied outputs and opinions based on age and ethnicities of the respondents. Overall, the results showed that the respondents' preferences were towards the quality of the food relating to the health and this preference accordingly has a good amount of impact on the restaurant chain or business. These results suggested that people are preferring a healthy way of living and choosing the quality restaurant food accordingly.

This study highlights the work that the restaurant business is influenced by several factors to an extent. In the literature we completely focused on the factors like analysis of existing market, Advertising, packaging strategies, and being updated and ensure the profits. And the survey conducted also proved the point that quality of the supply chain and the efficient packaging, combined work of the personnel at every level, marketing and promotional strategies plays an

equal role for the decent outcome of the food and linked with the profits of the business. In a way it also influences the healthy eating habits of the individuals.

According to the Boardman, 2017., there should be a predesigned plan for a business to execute successfully and our survey also proved and maximum percentage of people agreed with planning ahead helps to combat foreseen problems or issues. Fields, 2014., mentioned that success of the restaurant industry depends on the actions and quality interactions of all the structures at every level, and the respondents of the survey also agreed that the success of the restaurant business evolved by interactions at every level. He also mentioned that the place or location of the business greatly effects the restaurant profits i.e., inflow of the customers and this can be related to locations where there are high chances of natural calamities and less flow of customers so, strategic planning helps in comprehending this kind of issue.

Additionally, being up to date with the new technologies on the market and I would like to focus here on sustainable packaging technology that is plastic- free and that is biodegradable, which would be a great opportunity to attract customers. Biodegradable packaging is created using plastic generated from polymers that will break down with the assistance of living organisms. The edible packaging will gradually decompose over time without affecting the environment, even if consumers select not to eat it. Even most of the survey strongly agreed with the new packaging technique which is eco-friendly and potential enough in food industries to reduce lot of wastage.

Reduced environmental effect of plastic production and processing is made possible by biodegradable polymers. As agricultural waste and renewable feedstocks are used to make biodegradable polymers, there is a huge potential for research activity to capitalize on this business opportunity. Currently, just 1% of plastics are replaced by biodegradable polymers. To

extend the shelf life of various high-quality food goods, biodegradable packaging can be utilized for modified atmosphere packaging, active packaging systems, and edible packaging. Future research should concentrate on how sensors and nanotechnology may be used to communicate information to consumers. Biodegradable polymers can contribute to a more sustainable environment overall.

Limitations and Conclusion

This study does have some limitations and might be because of the study design used. The study design used is quantitative survey method. Data for small geographical areas also may be too unreliable to be useful as most of our survey responses are from Edmond, OK (college students) and from small parts (Hyderabad, Guntur, Vijayawada, etc.) of INDIA. The sample lacked diversity, and the results might not be applicable to people from more mixed ethnic, racial, geographic, and socioeconomic backgrounds. And a few of the survey questions are unanswered which also might affect our study.

This survey study and analysis helped us in a better understanding of the goals and objectives of a food business and practices to be followed for the success of the business. The results obtained were able to lead us to solve the probable issues raised while running the restaurant i.e., a predesigned plan is essential. It is also understood that success of the business is interlinked with actions and quality of interactions (Criteria, location, and caliber of menu) of personnel at every level of business.

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